

Exploring the Landscape of Ukrainian Natural Language Processing: Tools, Resources, and Research Trends

Anonymous ACL submission

Abstract

This article presents a review of existing resources, corpora, and datasets available for the Ukrainian language across various platforms, including CLARIN, Huggingface, and other major repositories. We explored a range of digital tools, platforms, and scientific datasets, evaluating their applicability for linguistic research and natural language processing (NLP) tasks involving Ukrainian. Additionally, the article explores scientific publications and databases such as Web of Science and Scopus, analyzing key parameters of research output focused on the Ukrainian language. By providing a detailed assessment of these resources, we aim to offer insights into their current status, accessibility, and future potential in advancing Ukrainian language technology and research.

1 Introduction

Natural Language Processing (NLP) has become a pivotal field in modern computational linguistics, bridging the gap between human language and machine understanding. While significant advancements have been made globally, the development of NLP tools, resources, and methodologies tailored to specific languages and cultural contexts remains a critical area of focus. Ukrainian, a language with rich linguistic structures and cultural heritage, presents unique challenges and opportunities for NLP researchers.

In recent years, the landscape of Ukrainian NLP has witnessed considerable growth, driven by the increasing need for language technologies that support applications such as machine translation, sentiment analysis, information retrieval, and text simplification. For example, the number of publications in the Scopus database has increased significantly over the last 3-4 years, which shows the growing interest in processing Ukrainian data (Figure 1). The development of a corpora, linguistic resources and machine learning models has been

Figure 1: Yearly distribution of research publications in Scopus database, which are related with Ukrainian NLP.

essential to address the complexities of Ukrainian, including its morphological richness, flexible syntax, and unique orthographic features.

This paper provides a comprehensive exploration of the current state of Ukrainian NLP, highlighting the tools and resources that have been developed, the challenges faced by researchers, and the emerging trends shaping the field. By examining these aspects, we aim to identify gaps in existing research, promote the creation of new resources, and foster collaboration within the NLP community.

Through this study, we aim to contribute to the ongoing discourse on language-specific NLP development, emphasizing the importance of preserving linguistic diversity while leveraging global advancements in computational linguistics.

2 General landscape overview

Over the last decade, researchers have started to pay more precise attention to the so-called non-English NLP, expanding current studies to mid-resource (Finnish, Serbian, Ukrainian, Hebrew, etc.) or low-resource languages (Wallisian, Lao, Bashkir, Khmer, etc.). It has appeared that those computational models, which were initially designed for processing English data, are truly limited in meeting all the requirements of such morphologically

rich inflectional languages as Ukrainian, so that their methods and techniques may be substantially harder to become fully customized to the peculiarities of MRLs (morphologically rich languages). Despite the fact that there is a lack of labeled resources available for the Ukrainian language, it is considered to be "the rising star", as shown by the recent assessment of a representation of marked dataset availability of high-, mid- and low-resource languages in well-known repositories (Joshi et al., 2020). This means that Ukrainian and other languages that belong to the same category (Indonesian, Cebuano, Afrikaans, Hebrew) have a great potential to become prosperous in the world of NLP systems down the line, primarily because of unsupervised pre-training that has proven a revolutionary enhancement for those languages. Yet, being sufficiently web-presented and having fairly powerful online cultural support, the putative "rising stars" at large and Ukrainian in particular have been far away from a state-of-the-art NLP breakthrough. One of the issues, according to NLP system developers, lies in the absence of high-quality annotated data that could further be used for creating new models or evaluating and fine-tuning currently existing models in a low- or mid-resource setting. However, the latest surge in the emergence of various models and tools for processing Ukrainian has ensured encouraging progress in this dimension of non-English NLP, on the one hand, and caused some reasonable concerns among Ukrainian linguists, on the other hand: newly created resources, models, and tools still do not cover the full scope of linguistic diversity in Ukrainian, particularly regional dialects and informal speech.

Taking this into account, we see our primary goal in analyzing the degree of provision of the Ukrainian language with datasets, models, tools and the level of their quality, which enables to identify the spectrum of data diversity (dialects, spoken forms, text genres, grammar and vocabulary variability, and so forth). Such a comprehensive approach will help to define the assets and weaknesses of the analyzed resources. But first, it is important to assess what has been contributed to the development of Ukrainian NLP by briefly reviewing the scope of publications devoted to recently developed corpora, datasets, models, tools of the Ukrainian language and tendencies concerning all these resources.

The vast majority of publications on Ukrainian corpora and datasets cover the data collected for

grammatical error correction (GEC), namely for improving speakers' fluency, grammar, punctuation, and spelling (Bondarenko et al., 2023; Syvokon et al., 2023; Fedchuk and Vysotska, 2024). A significant number of works are devoted to such tasks as morphological analysis and generation of out-of-vocabulary words enabled by lexicons extracted from certain corpora (Korobov, 2015), argumentation mining, authorship analysis (Scheffler et al., 2022), building embeddings, morphological paradigms and training POS and NER on them, creating POS tagging algorithms (Akbik et al., 2018; Babych, 2019), automatic speech recognition (Hamon and Grabar, 2017), punctuation restoration, training GPT models and fine-tuning (Kiulian et al., 2024; Kyrylov and Chaplynskyi, 2023), word-sense disambiguation (Laba et al., 2023), conceptual analysis, which combines semantics and pragmatics (Romanyshyn, 2018), text processing (Shvedova et al., 2021). There are also some studies that cover general-purpose corpora, such as GRAC, Zvidusil, etc. (Shvedova and von Waldenfels, 2021; Kotsyba et al., 2018; Darchuk, 2017).

Other publications are devoted to monolingual corpora of specific content (news, fiction, politics, medicine, corpora of a certain timespan, etc.), which allow to explore the Ukrainian language from the perspective of thematic vocabulary and use a corpus for machine training, namely for information retrieval and entity recognition, processing of unknown words, collocation analysis (Grabar and Hamon, 2018; Fischer et al., 2024), automatic morphological analysis of key terms within a corpus (Petrasova et al., 2017), POS disambiguation, testing spellchecking systems, NER models (Chaplynskyi and Romanyshyn, 2024; Starko and Rysin, 2023), morphological and syntactic disambiguation (Kotsyba and Moskalevskyi, 2019), text simplification (Cherednichenko et al., 2020), semantic tagging (Starko, 2021) and so forth.

Most articles are concerned with written corpora, while spoken ones are heavily underrepresented in Ukrainian NLP domain as they exist in little quantities and introduce only standard language (Dobrushina and Sokur, 2020).

Many research papers deal with the introduction and analysis of parallel bilingual (Mandziy et al., 2022; Popovych et al., 2023; Shvedova and Lukashevskyi, 2024; Vysotska et al., 2021) and multilingual (Grabar and Hamon, 2018; Grabar et al., 2018; Oleinik, 2024) corpora, among which Ukrainian is either the target or current source lan-

171 guage. Aligned corpora are represented as quite
172 diverse in terms of the purposes for which they can
173 be utilized: acquisition of bilingual lexicon for the
174 general and specific languages as well as the ac-
175 quisition of paraphrases (medical, legal, political,
176 military discourses, etc.), machine translation, con-
177 trastive studies, stylistic analysis, text analysis and
178 so forth.

179 When it comes to NLP models, the major-
180 ity of articles refer to Ukrainian language mod-
181 eling based on existing well-recognized tools,
182 such as BERT, RoBERTa, ALBERT, DistilBERT,
183 Word2vec, AGAT, ELECTRA, XLM-R large, As-
184 spell, mT5, etc. Some of them represent tasks
185 that encompass measuring syntactic and semantic
186 word similarities pre-trained on sizeable datasets
187 (Haltiuk and Smywiński-Pohl, 2024; Sineglazov
188 and Savenko, 2024), sentiment analysis (Prytula,
189 2024; Shakhovska et al., 2020), automatic morpho-
190 logical, syntactic and semantic analysis (Darchuk
191 et al., 2023), text classification (Dementieva et al.,
192 2023), text embedding (Bisikalo et al., 2023), gram-
193 matical error correction (Palma Gomez et al., 2023),
194 speech recognition (Dumyn et al., 2024), machine
195 translation (Konyk et al., 2023) and so on.

196 In recent years, large language models (LLMs)
197 have significantly impacted the development of nat-
198 ural language processing (NLP). The growing fo-
199 cus on Ukrainian-specific LLMs was evident at
200 the Third Ukrainian Natural Language Processing
201 Workshop (UNLP) held in conjunction with LREC-
202 COLING 2024¹.

203 A central development in this area was the UNLP
204 2024 Shared Task, the first competition centered
205 on fine-tuning LLMs for Ukrainian (Romanyshyn
206 et al., 2024). The task’s primary objective was
207 to advance models capable of generating fluent,
208 culturally and historically informed responses in
209 Ukrainian. For reproducibility and transparency,
210 participants were required to use publicly available
211 models of moderate size.

212 Papers (Kiulian et al., 2024; Boros et al., 2024)
213 were focused on fine-tuning open-source LLMs,
214 such as Gemma and Mistral, using Ukrainian-
215 specific datasets.

216 In addition to fine-tuning existing models, an-
217 other important contribution is the Spivavtor
218 dataset and the instruction-tuned models designed
219 for Ukrainian text editing tasks. Spivavtor (Saini
220 et al., 2024) adapts instruction-based tasks like

221 grammatical error correction, text simplification,
222 coherence improvement, and paraphrasing to the
223 Ukrainian language.

224 Additionally, the Eval-UA-tion suite offers a
225 collection of evaluation datasets specifically de-
226 signed to assess the performance of language mod-
227 els in Ukrainian (Hamotskyi et al., 2024). These
228 include the UA-CBT task, which evaluates narra-
229 tive comprehension, UP-Titles, a task that matches
230 articles with corresponding titles, and LMentry-
231 static-UA/LMES, which focuses on tasks that are
232 challenging for language models but simple for
233 humans.

234 Overall, the scope of publications reviewed
235 above illustrates a significant growth of Ukrainian
236 natural language processing. This growth has been
237 driven by multiple factors, including the increasing
238 global attention to underrepresented languages and
239 the establishment of the international annual work-
240 shop UNLP². The UNLP conference has become
241 a central platform for consolidating academic and
242 industrial efforts, improving collaboration, and ad-
243 vancing research focused specifically on Ukrainian
244 language technologies.

245 **3 Analysis of linguistic resources and** 246 **tools for the Ukrainian language**

247 **3.1 Overview of analyzed platforms for** 248 **linguistic resource and tool evaluation**

249 To gather a comprehensive view of available re-
250 sources for the Ukrainian language, we analyzed
251 four major platforms: ELG³, CLARIN⁴, ELRA⁵,
252 and Hugging Face⁶. These repositories vary in
253 focus—some are richer in corpora, datasets, and
254 lexical materials (e.g., ELG, ELRA, CLARIN,
255 GitHub), while others primarily host models and
256 processing tools (notably ELG and Hugging Face).

257 The European Language Grid (ELG) currently
258 hosts over 13,000 language technology products,
259 offering both commercial and non-commercial
260 resources. For Ukrainian, ELG provides 261
261 entries, including 122 corpora (mostly bilingual
262 or multilingual), 123 tools and services, and 16
263 lexical/conceptual resources such as dictionaries
264 and thesauruses. CLARIN, part of the Euro-
265 pean Research Infrastructure Consortium, offers

²<https://unlp.org.ua/>

³<https://live.european-language-grid.eu/>

⁴<https://vlo.clarin.eu/>

⁵<https://catalogue.elra.info/en-us/>

⁶<https://huggingface.co/>

¹<https://aclanthology.org/volumes/2024.unlp-1/>

77 Ukrainian corpora—predominantly multilingual—along with 50 datasets, 18 tools/webservices, and 10 lexical resources.

The ELRA platform plays a more limited role in Ukrainian NLP. It offers only two multilingual corpora and one monolingual corpus of read speech for speech recognition research. Additionally, it lists seven lexical-conceptual resources.

Hugging Face⁷ stands out for its abundance of Ukrainian models—over 1000 language resources, many of which were developed by the community. While this platform fosters open collaboration and experimentation, many resources lack sufficient documentation or high-quality metadata, which limits their reliability and usability. Finally, our survey also includes repositories like GitHub⁸ and lang-uk⁹, which host diverse tools and datasets supporting tasks such as translation, morphological analysis, classification, and word embedding.

3.2 Data analysis

3.2.1 Analysis of linguistic resources

As a result of the analysis of various platforms and resources listed in section 2.1, about 145 different corpora and datasets were found (the data was collected in October 2024). The distribution of resources (corpora and datasets) by source is presented in Figure 2. All the resources found were systematized and posted on the website of the Ukrainian CLARIN K-Center¹⁰. K-Center’s website already has resources, so there are about 170 resources for the Ukrainian language.

⁷<https://huggingface.co/>

⁸<https://github.com/>

⁹<https://lang.org.ua/>

¹⁰<https://uacorporus.org/k-centre/>

Figure 2: Distribution of resources (corpora and datasets) depending on its type (monolingual, bilingual, multilingual).

We analyzed the newly found resources according to their type (monolingual, bilingual, multilingual). As you can see in Figure 3, the majority of resources are multilingual, and Ukrainian is one of them. In second place by quantity are resources that are monolingual, namely in Ukrainian. There are not many of them, only 42, but they are quite diverse. And in last place are bilingual resources, which are most often parallel corpora.

Figure 3: Distribution of resources (corpora and datasets) by source.

It was most interesting to analyze the tasks that these resources cover. The result is presented in Figure 4, it is clear that most resources were created for the task of machine translation (about 48%), then resources for language identification, speech recognition, NER, text generation, parsing, text categorization, PoS tagging, and text summarization are well represented, however, they are not presented in such quantity as for the task of machine translation and sometimes it is 1-2 resources, no more.

3.2.2 Tool analysis

If we examine the existing tools for the Ukrainian language (Figure 2), we can observe that the majority are available on the Huggingface platform.

Figure 4: Distribution of resources (corpora and datasets) by task.

This is largely due to the fact that most of the individuals developing new models are developers and enthusiasts working on personal initiatives.

However, it is important to note that models and data on this platform may have poor metadata and description, making them difficult to use.

If we look at Figure 4 and Figure 5, we can see that for both resources and tools, the machine translation task is the leader and quite popular. But if we look at the subsequent tasks, we see that for tools, models of voice recognition and feature extraction, text classification, and embeddings have a special influence. But for data, the priority tasks are language detection, morphological analysis, syntactic parsing, and universal dependencies. As a result, we can say that tools have achieved greater coverage of tasks compared to data.

4 Research trends in Ukrainian NLP

The development of Natural Language Processing (NLP) for Ukrainian has grown substantially, as evidenced by an analysis of key themes in recent academic publications. This section highlights the primary research trends derived from recurring keywords and topics, shedding light on the priorities and challenges within the field.

As a source of data for the analysis of modern trends in Ukrainian NLP, we took the data from the ACL anthology¹¹ database and bibliographic descriptions related to the processing of Ukrainian in Scopus and Web of Science.

The data was collected in November 2024 and presented in Table 1.

We have analyzed the most frequent keywords in bibliographic publications from the Scopus and Web of Science (WoS) bibliographic databases and

¹¹<https://aclanthology.org/>

Figure 5: Distribution of tools by task.

Figure 6: WoS keyword frequency dynamics over time.

Figure 7: Scopus keyword frequency dynamics over time.

presented them in the following Figure 6 and Figure 7.

The graphs in Figure 6 illustrate the trends of the most popular keywords in the Web of Science database. They show a general increase in the number of publications related to Ukrainian language processing beginning around 2019. Additionally, for high-frequency keywords such as "machine translation," "NLP," and "machine learning," a sharp rise in publications is evident.

Figure 7 presents data from Scopus, showing a significant surge in publications related to machine translation since 2022. This trend is likely associated with the onset of full-scale military actions in Ukraine, which led to a large number of Ukrainian refugees abroad. As a result, many European countries accelerated the development of machine translation applications and datasets to meet the demand.

Furthermore, as previously shown, machine translation has received the most resources and model development. Meanwhile, the number of publications specifically related to the Ukrainian language has also been increasing since approxi-

Number	ACL anthology	Web of Science	Scopus
Conference paper	75	109	516
Article	1	208	228
Book chapter	-	0	15
Review	-	109	516
Total number of citations	-	681	3395
Number of articles with zero citations	-	182	260
Total number of papers	76	317	771

Table 1: General information on Ukrainian publications from ACL anthology, Web of Science, and Scopus.

Figure 8: The most frequent tasks (based on Scopus and WoS data).

mately 2020–2021 (marked by the red line in the graph).

5 Most frequent tasks for Ukrainian NLP

In order to determine the tasks most frequently studied, we analyzed keywords from Scopus and WoS publications related to the processing of the Ukrainian language. As a result, the following tasks were identified: *Machine Translation*, *Sentiment Analysis*, *Information Extraction*, *Linguistic Analysis*, *Text Classification*, *Named Entity Recognition (NER)*, *Lemmatization*, *Stemming* and *Dependency Parsing*. In addition, several studies focus on corpus and lexicographic research, including *GRAC (General Regionally Annotated Corpus of Ukrainian Language)*, *Ontology*, *Corpus*, *Content Analysis*, *Corpus Linguistics*, and *VESUM*. More details on the frequency of these words are shown in Figure 8.

In our paper, we focus on tokenizers, lemmatizers, and POS taggers, as they serve as fundamental building blocks for many NLP applications, enabling accurate text processing and linguistic analysis. Covering all NLP tasks in detail is beyond the scope of this study; for more information on NER (Chaplynskyi and Romanyshyn, 2024), Sentiment Analysis (Prytula, 2024; Shakhovska et al., 2020),

Corpus Linguistics (Shvedova and Lukashevskyi, 2024; Starko, 2021), and Vesum (Starko and Rysin, 2022), we refer to the corresponding publications.

5.1 Overview of tokenizers, lemmatizers, and POS taggers

The Ukrainian language presents unique challenges for text processing, including complex morphology, rich inflectional paradigms, and specific orthographic rules. Several tools have been developed to address these challenges, focusing on tokenization, lemmatization, and part-of-speech (POS) tagging.

Available tokenizers:

1. Stanza (Stanford NLP)¹²

This tool realizes tokenization, multi-word expression (if applicable), POS, Lemma, and dependency parsing is provided using data from Universal Dependencies (UD) v2.12. However, since the Ukrainian UD was developed quite a long time ago, and the UD marking rules themselves have already been slightly modified, the accuracy of this model for the Ukrainian language is quite low, and this model requires improvement.

2. spaCy¹³

Uses statistical models trained on Ukrainian corpora. Efficient for standard text but may struggle with domain-specific vocabulary. Information on the accuracy of Spacey’s models is available on the model’s website, with an accuracy of 0.95 for the morphological analysis, and for the named entities recognition, the F-score is 0.87. The values presented on the site are not bad, but in practice, it is clear that the model still makes quite a few mistakes when working with Ukrainian data.

¹²<https://stanfordnlp.github.io/stanza/tokenize.html>

¹³<https://spacy.io/models/uk>

- 441 3. **UDPipe**¹⁴
- 442 UDPipe is a trainable pipeline for tokeniza-
- 443 tion, tagging, lemmatization and dependency
- 444 analysis of CoNLL-U files. However, for
- 445 the Ukrainian language, the same problem
- 446 remains, UD is not updated.
- 447 4. **Tokenizers, lemmitizer from lang-uk**¹⁵
- 448 Rule-based tokenizer available for Ukrainian.
- 449 Less robust for complex texts compared to
- 450 modern neural approaches.
- 451 5. **pymorphy3**¹⁶
- 452 A rule-based morphological analyzer and POS
- 453 tagger for Ukrainian. Uses a large dictionary
- 454 of Ukrainian word forms. This tool provides
- 455 lemmatization, POS tagging, and inflection.
- 456 6. **TreeTagger**¹⁷
- 457 TreeTagger is a tool for annotating text with
- 458 information about parts of speech and lemmas,
- 459 uses a statistical model, but for the Ukrainian
- 460 language it was trained on UD Treebank.
- 461 7. **LanguageTool API NLP UK**¹⁸

462 The work (Starko and Rysin, 2023) announced

463 the gold dataset for the evaluation of PoS models

464 for the Ukrainian language. The authors realized a

465 subset¹⁹ that was manually checked.

466 6 NLP tasks requiring attention

467 Using the same method of extracting keywords

468 from Scopus and WoS publications, we identified

469 tasks that receive inadequate attention in the realm

470 of Ukrainian NLP. Thus, the least well-represented

471 in terms of available tools, models, and datasets are

472 Word Sense Disambiguation (WSD) and Corefer-

473 ence Resolution (CR). The reason is that, unlike

474 Machine Translation (MT), Named Entity Recogni-

475 tion (NER), or Part-of-Speech (POS) tagging, they

476 satisfy industrial needs less (e.g., automated cus-

477 tomer service, chatbots, search engines, etc.) and

478 therefore are being overlooked by computational

479 linguists. Such a tendency can be explained by

¹⁴<https://ufal.mff.cuni.cz/udpipe/2/models>

¹⁵<https://lang.org.ua/en/>

¹⁶<https://pypi.org/project/pymorphy3/>

¹⁷<https://www.cis.uni-muenchen.de/schmid/tools/TreeTagger/Windows>

¹⁸[https://github.com/brown-uk/nlp_uk?tab = readme - ov - file](https://github.com/brown-uk/nlp_uk?tab=readme-ov-file)

¹⁹<https://github.com/brown-uk/corpus/tree/master/data/good>

WSD and CR's peculiar requirements for resources

aimed at dealing with them: i) the need for ex-

tensive, manually annotated monolingual datasets

demanding thorough linguistic expertise; ii) the

decisive role of context in coping with polysemy

(WSD) or expressions related to the same entity

(CR); iii) fine-tuning of existing models that neces-

sitates understanding of Ukrainian-specific corefer-

ence structures and variations in word interpreta-

tion.

6.1 Models and tools devoted to coreference resolution

1. Coref-UA Model²⁰

The model was developed by Artem Kramov

and Andrii Kursin, who used the F-Coref

library as a basis and utilised the Silver

Ukrainian Coreference Dataset for training.

For the purposes of Ukrainian-specific corefer-

ence resolution, the XML-Roberta base model

was fine-tuned. Coref-UA Model offers such

functionalities as the prediction of coreference

clusters and extraction of logits for entity pairs.

According to the developers, the coreference

precision reaches 0.758.

2. Fastcoref-UA²¹

Fastcoref-UA is a version of the FastCoref

package modified for the Ukrainian language-

specific needs. It allows users to extract

"coreference clusters (either as strings or as

character indices over the original texts) as

well as the logits for each corefering entity

pair". While the available description of

Fastcoref-UA provides some insight into its

functional properties, there is no information

concerning the model's accuracy evaluation.

3. Coreferent Clusters Web Service²²

The Docker-based HTTP Web Service devel-

oped by Artem Kramov identifies coreferent

pairs in Ukrainian corpora. It harnesses the

MySQL database, which is comprised of an

annotated set of Ukrainian texts with corefer-

ent groups and additional information (e.g.,

Lemma, Cases, etc.) for each token. The pre-

cise performance metrics are not mentioned

on the Web Service's page. This information

²⁰<https://huggingface.co/artemkramov/coref-ua>

²¹<https://github.com/artemkramov/fastcoref-ua>

²²<https://data.mendeley.com/datasets/mb77zhxynt/1>

525	requires consulting official documentation or	social media texts, dialectal variations, and code-	571
526	contacting the resource’s developers.	switching with Russian or Surzhyk. Additionally,	572
527	6.2 Models and tools devoted to word sense	while there has been a rise in transformer-based	573
528	disambiguation	models for Ukrainian, such as Ukrainian BERT,	574
529	1. ukr-paraphrase-multilingual-mpnet-base	research on large-scale Ukrainian LLMs remains	575
530	²³	limited compared to better-resourced languages.	576
531	The model is based on the supervised fine-	Overall, while Ukrainian NLP has made con-	577
532	tuning of a pre-trained Large Language Model	siderable progress, much work is still needed to	578
533	(LLM) and deals with the extraction of con-	expand resources, improve model generalization,	579
534	textual embeddings for words with multiple	and address linguistic challenges unique to the	580
535	senses. Designed for clustering and semantic	Ukrainian language.	581
536	search, it shows 77.9 per cent accuracy for the		
537	prediction of homonyms.	8 Conclusions	582
538	2. U-WSD (Contextual Embeddings for	The increasing interest in Ukrainian NLP presents	583
539	Ukrainian) ²⁴	an opportunity for large-scale data collection and	584
540	This is a fine-tuned ConEFU model for the	model training. However, achieving comprehen-	585
541	Ukrainian language, which is based on the S-	sive NLP support for Ukrainian will require:	586
542	BERT model adapted using an unsupervised		
543	triplet dataset built on UberText2.0. It shows	• Expanding high-quality annotated corpora, es-	587
544	high performance in choosing between correct	pecially for low-resource tasks.	588
545	and incorrect senses of homonyms.	• Developing domain-specific NLP applica-	589
546		tions, including medical, legal, and historical	590
547	7 Discussion	texts.	591
548	Our analysis of Ukrainian NLP tools, resources,	• Addressing linguistic variability by incorpo-	592
549	and research trends highlights both significant	rating dialects, code-switching, and Surzhyk.	593
550	progress and critical gaps in the field. While		
551	some fundamental NLP tasks, such as tokeniza-	Future research should focus on building a sus-	594
552	tion, lemmatization, and POS tagging, have well-	tainable NLP ecosystem for Ukrainian, including	595
553	established tools like Stanza, UDPipe, and py-	open-source resources, interdisciplinary collabora-	596
554	morphy2, other areas—particularly those requiring	tions, and industry-academia partnerships. Given	597
555	large-scale annotated corpora—remain underdevel-	the rapid evolution of language technology, invest-	598
556	oped.	ing in language-specific large language models	599
557	One of the most notable advancements has been	(LLMs) and improving cross-lingual transfer learn-	600
558	in machine translation, where state-of-the-art mod-	ing techniques could significantly benefit Ukrainian	601
559	els such as Google Translate, Meta AI models, and	NLP.	602
560	OPUS-MT have significantly improved Ukrainian-	By tackling these challenges, we can create a	603
561	English translation quality. However, the lack of	more inclusive and linguistically diverse NLP envi-	604
562	high-quality parallel corpora still poses chal-	ronment, ensuring that the Ukrainian language is	605
563	lenges for further refinement, especially for low-	effectively supported in the age of modern AI and	606
564	resource language pairs involving Ukrainian. Simi-	digital communication.	607
565	larly, while Named Entity Recognition (NER) has	Limitations	608
566	seen some success with Ukrainian-specific datasets,	The authors of this paper have attempted to provide	609
567	the domain coverage remains limited, and models	a comprehensive overview of the current Ukrainian	610
568	struggle with historical texts and named entity am-	NLP landscape, it should be admitted that it is	611
569	biguity.	still limited, as each task requires specific attention.	612
570	Sentiment analysis and text classification suffer	Second, the rapidly evolving nature of the field	613
	from data scarcity, especially when dealing with	means that some recent developments, particularly	614
		those that occurred after our data collection phase,	615
		may not be included in the analysis. Given the	616

²³<https://huggingface.co/lang-uk/ukr-paraphrase-multilingual-mpnet-base>

²⁴<https://github.com/YuriiLaba/U-WSD>

617 increasing pace of model releases, dataset publica-
618 tions, and research results, the landscape is inher-
619 ently dynamic and time-sensitive.

620 Third, while we aimed to include a wide range
621 of tools and resources, the review may not fully
622 cover non-publicly documented or proprietary sys-
623 tems, particularly those developed for commercial
624 use or internal academic applications. Likewise,
625 resources and projects that are poorly documented,
626 only available in Ukrainian, or hosted on less vis-
627 ible platforms may have been inadvertently ex-
628 cluded due to discovery issues.

629 Fourth, our review primarily focuses on text-
630 based NLP. Other modalities (such as speech, mul-
631 timodal systems, or sign language processing) are
632 not considered in detail, although they represent
633 important and growing areas of Ukrainian language
634 technology. In addition, while we acknowledge the
635 value of linguistic diversity and regional dialects
636 in Ukrainian, most of the resources analyzed are
637 based on standard Ukrainian, which may not reflect
638 the full linguistic variability of real-world usage.

639 Despite these limitations, however, we believe
640 that this study provides a valuable basis for under-
641 standing the current state of Ukrainian NLP and
642 identifying key areas for future research and devel-
643 opment.

644 Acknowledgments

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